

Entrepreneurial Resilience, Costly Signals and Innovative Behavior in Crisis: A Behavioral Ecology Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The role of psychological resources in entrepreneurial resilience has been extensively discussed and empirically analyzed in many studies. However, an interdisciplinary approach to how resilience enables entrepreneurs to generate costly signals of innovative behavior was not introduced in a scholarly conversation. This complex and challenging exploration on multiple disciplines, drawn from the entrepreneurial resilience and costly signaling theories and integrating insights from behavioral ecology, offers a new perspective on innovative behavior under adverse conditions. A theory synthesis and a cross-disciplinary approach were adopted to analyze the insights from entrepreneurial psychology, resilience research, behavioral ecology, and innovation. A novel conceptual framework and propositions on stress responses, anxiety, and entrepreneurial resilience describe how entrepreneurs could generate costly signals of innovative behavior. This exploratory study proposes that entrepreneurs experiencing anxiety or stress are more likely to generate low-cost signaling, resulting in less credible signals of innovation, which may reduce consumer confidence in their products and services. It provides insights for both scholars and practitioners, offering a foundation for developing strategies that strengthen resilience and foster innovation in crisis contexts.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial resilience, psychological resources, costly signaling, behavioral ecology, innovation, crisis.

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurs' mental health and well-being (MWB) are valuable internal resources enhancing entrepreneurial resilience in uncertain economic environments. Scholars often employ the concept of resilience to describe entrepreneurs' preparedness, hardiness, persistence, or self-efficacy, explaining performance differences between resilient and non-resilient entrepreneurs (Farchi & Peled-Avram, 2025; Korber & McNaughton, 2018). Furthermore, the cognitive and entrepreneurial traits of social entrepreneurs enable organizations to adapt to changing environments and contribute to long-term sustainability through innovation (Raman et al., 2025; Biggs et al., 2010). Ayed et al. (2019) and Huggins et al. (2014) conceptualize resilience as a multidimensional construct encompassing psychological, social, cultural, and biological processes that enable individuals to adapt to changing environments and resist events that threaten their well-being within social, family, and personal contexts.

Resilience of entrepreneurs is instrumental to overcoming adverse conditions (Shepherd & Williams, 2020), but how do stress responses and anxiety affect resilience? How does resilience enable entrepreneurs to generate costly signals that stimulate innovation within organizations in crisis? Empirical evidence suggests that job stress negatively impacts employees' innovation, although other studies have found a non-significant relationship between job stress and innovative behavior (Montani & Stagliano, 2022; Bani-Melhem et al., 2020; Bani-Melhem et al., 2018). Conversely, research indicates that happy entrepreneurs are more innovative in the long term and develop better products and services for their customers and partners (Mukerjee et al., 2026; Stephan, 2018; Gavin & Mason, 2004).

First, this conceptual paper contributes to theory by integrating individual psychological resources with entrepreneurial resilience and by theorizing signaling as a mediator between resilience and innovative behavior. Second, it develops a conceptual framework that outlines the relationships among key variables, including stress responses, anxiety, resilience, signaling, innovative behavior, and crisis. Third, the study advances three research propositions for future empirical testing. Finally, the findings provide a foundation for shaping innovation strategies for businesses operating in times of distress.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Psychological resources and innovation

The costs associated with negative well-being are substantial and disproportionate to the benefits derived from maintaining well-being and innovation in business. Poor mental health is expected to cause an economic burden globally (World Health Organization, 2025; OECD, 2026). Entrepreneurs are less innovative, persistent, and productive when their well-being suffers (Stephan, 2022), leading to lower economic output and fewer jobs.

Psychological resources constitute strategic assets for entrepreneurs, enabling them to build resilience, drive innovation, and sustain business performance. They are conceptualized as internal capacities inherent to the individual, developed at the psychological level (Pellerin et al., 2026; Csillik, 2017). Bui et al. (2025) and Najjinda et al. (2024) proposed that entrepreneurial resources such as skills, knowledge, and competencies can facilitate women entrepreneurs to manage successful ventures while meeting their family, personal, and social needs. Several studies have shown that psychological resources, which foster mental health resilience during life-challenging times, exert protective effects on well-being and reduce psychological distress (Pellerin et al., 2026). According to Hobfoll et al. (2018), individuals with greater resources, including psychological resources and positive outcomes, are more likely to experience resource gain spirals, rendering them less vulnerable to resource depletion and capable of accumulating additional resources.

2.2 Entrepreneurial resilience theory

Resilience theory has examined entrepreneurial failure and recovery processes, emphasizing the significance of psychological traits and resilience mechanisms that enable entrepreneurs to recover from business failures and continue engaging in entrepreneurial activities (Wagner et al., 2021; Korber & McNaughton, 2018). In this context, resilience is conceptualized as the capacity to utilize resources in adverse environments (Yu & Chen, 2025). Resilience is also associated with reduced depression, anxiety, and emotional exhaustion, improving the life quality of people (Mukerjee et al., 2026; Connor & Davidson, 2003; Herrman et al., 2011; Luthar et al., 2000).

Ahmed et al. (2022), through a meta-analytic review of psychological resilience, individual stress, and coping mechanisms, raised some issues concerning the interchange between stressors and resilience-development processes. The development of their framework included three resilience dimensions: 1. hardiness (encompassing commitment, control, and challenge orientation), 2. resourcefulness (the ability to mobilize resources during adversity), and 3. optimism (positive future expectations despite setbacks). Additionally, a five-year longitudinal study by Ayala and Manzano (2014) found that the three dimensions of resilience (hardiness, resourcefulness, and optimism) contribute to 32.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial success, with hardiness emerging as the most robust predictor of sustained business performance (Pellerin et al., 2026). Similarly, Korber and McNaughton (2018) focused on understanding entrepreneurs' need for resilience and their coping efforts in the context of environmental and structural challenges. Scholars recommended an in-depth investigation into entrepreneur stress, resilience, and coping mechanisms to understand the ability to withstand adversity and adaptability in distressed environments (Wagner et al., 2021; Ahmed, 2022).

2.3 Costly signaling theory and behavioral ecology

Zahavi (1975) developed the model of the handicap principle by explaining the quality and reliability of a message. The appearance of a person or animal communicates a variety of signals to its surrounding environment. For example, mating is a channel for sending sexual signals to organisms. An individual who has passed the mating test is seen as high-quality. A female could discriminate between a male possessing sexual characteristics and a male who does not possess the characteristics and pass the test. Thus, the cost of a signal is assessed from a multilevel perspective by males and females.

The reliability of a signal constitutes a major dimension of the costly signaling theory and is sustained in different signaling systems due to the mutual interests of the sender and receiver. Maynard-Smith and Harper (2003) further emphasized that signal reliability is a fundamental component in theories of signal evolution. However, reliability becomes problematic when senders attempt to mislead signal receivers, particularly when they have incentives to perform this act. Fraser (2012) examined this issue across various contexts, including mate choice, alarm calling, and predator-prey interactions. In a frequent form, signalers present themselves as stronger and more desirable than in reality to take advantage of a wrong impression from receivers. Conversely,

Zahavi (1975) argued that signal reliability depends on the difficulty of performance related to the quality and quantity.

Finally, costly signaling theory provides an alternative framework for understanding resource sharing as a form of signaling through which individuals flaunt their hidden qualities (Gintis et al., 2001; Zahavi, 1995). Gintis et al. (2001) further argue that engagement in costly signaling through substantial investments of time, energy, and resources distinguishes individuals from others. McAndrew (2021) explains that individuals engage in behaviors that are costly to convince people of the validity of the information about themselves. Similarly, Fraser (2012) explains that individuals convey qualities that are costly to obtain and difficult to fake, such as intelligence and genetic endowment.

2.4 Entrepreneurs' resilience and costly signals

The present study explores how individual psychological resources (Hartmann et al., 2022) impact resilience, thereby enabling entrepreneurs to generate signals of innovative behavior. The cost of signaling and the quality of the signals concerning the meaning and/or validity depend on the condition or the environment (Fraser, 2012). Imbrie, Daniels, and Toner (2023) explained that signals can be financial or reputational, or risky concerning the loss of human lives, such as the deployment of troops on battlefields. The actual value of a costly signal depends on the price being paid by the senders if they back down on their promise or threat.

Extending this perspective to entrepreneurship, high signaling costs are borne by high-quality individuals possessing a strong resilience. In contrast, individuals with low or no resilience are unable to absorb such costs and therefore either refrain from signaling or signal at a reduced intensity commensurate with their level of quality. Conversely, entrepreneurs experiencing anxiety or stress are more likely to generate low-cost signaling, resulting in less credible signals of innovation, which may reduce consumer confidence in their products and services.

Table 1:

<p>Psychological resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Psychological resources, which foster mental health resilience during life-challenging times, exert protective effects on well-being and reduce psychological distress - Individuals with greater resources, including psychological resources and positive outcomes, are more likely to experience resource gain spirals, rendering them less vulnerable to resource depletion and capable of accumulating additional resources 	<p>(Pellerin et al., 2026)</p> <p>(Hobfoll et al., 2018)</p>
<p>Entrepreneurial resilience</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The protective role of resilience and higher levels of resilience were connected to lower psychological distress during Covid-19 	<p>(Yu & Chen, 2025)</p> <p>(Killgore et al., 2020)</p> <p>(Ran et al., 2020)</p>
<p>Costly signals</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The cost of signaling and the quality of the signals concerning the meaning and/or validity depend on the condition or the environment - Signal reliability is a fundamental component in theories of signal evolution 	<p>(Fraser, 2012)</p> <p>(Maynard-Smith & Harper, 2003)</p>
<p>Innovation</p>	<p>Entrepreneurs are less innovative, persistent, and productive when their well-being suffers, leading to lower economic output and fewer jobs</p>	<p>(Stephan, 2022)</p>

Source: *Created by Author*

3. Methods

A theory synthesis is adopted to analyze an unexplored scholarly area that can advance our understanding of how psychological resources enhance resilience and enable entrepreneurs to generate costly signals that stimulate innovation within organizations in a distressed environment. Principal research on the entrepreneurial resilience and costly signaling theories informed the theoretical development of this study. The application of this methodological approach enhanced

the integration of theoretical perspectives while providing a breadth of relevant scholarship across disciplines that employ diverse terminologies and conceptual frameworks (Omazic, 2021).

Additionally, a cross-disciplinary synthesis (Stewart & Winston, 2025) was also employed to identify commonalities, patterns, contradictions, gaps, and defining qualities among psychological resources, resilience, costly signaling, and innovative behavior in crisis contexts (Snyder, 2019; Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Booth et al., 2016). Insights from entrepreneurial psychology, resilience research, behavioral ecology, and innovation were integrated to develop a comprehensive scholarly analysis of these interrelated factors. While proposing a new direction drawn from an interdisciplinary perspective, the purpose of this conceptual paper is to develop rational and complete propositions concerning these associations rather than testing them empirically (Lim, 2026; Luna et al., 2015; Gilson & Goldberg, 2015).

A systematic search of articles, books, audio-visual materials, and other scholarly manuscripts was conducted across online databases, including EBSCO, Business Source Ultimate, science databases, ABI/INFORM Collection, and Proquest and other scientific databases. The search was guided by the following criteria: (1) entrepreneurs' well-being and mental health and psychological resources; (2) entrepreneurial resilience theory and resilience resources; (3) costly signaling theory and behavioral ecology; (4) innovation and innovative behavior; (5) published in peer-reviewed journals, academic books, or conference proceedings; and (6) available in the English language.

Exclusion criteria eliminated studies that concentrate on the following: (1) entrepreneurs' well-being and mental health, focused on the employee appraisal process and human resources, (2) entrepreneurial resilience in corporate governance, (3) innovation in normative economic environments, and (4) lack of methodological transparency for empirical studies. Opinion manuscripts, editorials, and non-peer-reviewed articles were excluded from the analysis of the scientific terms of the research themes (Stewart & Winston, 2025).

The literature review included eighty-five studies and two books by authors examining entrepreneurs' well-being, mental health, psychological resources, entrepreneurial resilience, and innovation. Additionally, eight studies by Amotz Zahavi, sourced from the Dead Sea and Arava Science Center online database, were included. Furthermore, seven studies and one book by

various authors focusing on costly signaling theory and behavioral ecology were incorporated in the thematic development.

This literature review is subject to several limitations, including potential language bias through English-only sources, as well as the relative scarcity of research examining the intersection of psychological resources, costly signaling, and entrepreneurs' signals concerning innovative behavior. Although a limited number of studies explicitly address entrepreneurs' psychological factors in shaping innovative behavior, the comprehensive body of research on entrepreneurial resilience provides a resourceful foundation for a constructive development of the proposed framework. Furthermore, insights from behavioral ecology and costly signals contribute to a deeper understanding of the significance of signals in enabling innovative behavior among entrepreneurs.

4. Results and Analysis

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

Interconnection of entrepreneurs' psychological resources, resilience, costly signaling, and innovative behavior in crisis.

Source: *Created by Author*

Entrepreneurs' psychological resources are instrumental in building resilience in times of crisis. Psychological resources are conceptualized as internal capacities inherent to the individual, developed at the psychological level (Pellerin et al., 2026; Csillik, 2017). In this context, stress

and anxiety affect entrepreneurs' psychological states, while resilience enhances their capabilities for innovative behavior. Furthermore, Stephan (2018), Gavin, and Mason (2004) argued that happy entrepreneurs are more innovative in the long term and develop better products and services for their customers and partners.

Consequently, in stable economic environments, entrepreneurs are capable of transmitting reliable signals to relevant audiences. In contrast, under adverse economic conditions where entrepreneurs face stress and anxiety, they may struggle to convince stakeholders of the validity, reliability, quality, and intensity of their signals. According to Zahavi's (1975) costly signaling theory and the handicap principle, high-cost signals are produced by reliable and credible individuals who demonstrate their trustworthiness by keeping their promises even in stressful circumstances. Rafique et al. (2022) identified a relationship between job stress and innovative work behavior (IWB), whereas Mukerjee (2026) and Ren and Zhang (2015) supported that stress could spark or defuse creativity and employees' IWB. Both authors supported that stress may positively impact a workplace if tasks have strict deadlines. Additionally, Slåtten and Mehmetoglu (2015) emphasized the effect of job stress on employees' innovative behavior, and Shaker et al. (2020) concentrated on employees' ability to innovate and present creative ideas at work.

Proposition 1:

Entrepreneurs experiencing low levels of stress during crises are more likely to develop strong resilience, which enables them to generate high-cost signals of innovative behavior.

Scholars recognize the significant challenges and setbacks entrepreneurs encounter in creating and sustaining new ventures (Corner et al. 2017). Schiff et al. (2025) and Samma et al. (2020) explain the implications of anxiety through the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory (Hobfoll, 2018), whereby anxiety arises from factors that pose actual or potential threats to the organization's valuable resources (Rasool, 2019). Anxiety can deplete both intangible and tangible resources, including resourcefulness, preparedness, self-efficacy, optimism, hardiness, and persistence.

Fraser (2012) explained that signals vary across individuals in size, intensity, and frequency, where not all signals are equally costly. The engagement in costly signaling and investment in excessive amounts of time, energy, and resources distinguishes an individual from

other people (McAndrew, 2021). Sometimes individuals flaunt their hidden qualities to generate costly and high-quality signals concerning their resources (well-being, intelligence, innovative behavior) (Gintis et al., 2001; Zahavi, 1995). However, the cost of signaling and the quality of the signals concerning the meaning and/or validity depend on the condition or the environment (Fraser, 2012). Individuals who cannot afford the signaling cost either don't signal at all or communicate at a lesser intensity that is nonetheless reasonable for their level of quality. Thus, entrepreneurs who are overwhelmed with anxiety and stress in an adverse condition cannot generate high-cost signals reflecting an innovative behavior. Therefore, entrepreneurs are expected to generate and intensify reliable and quality signals of their innovative behavior to earn consumers' trust. As a result, innovative strategies are more likely to be implemented in environments that enable entrepreneurs to project their qualities in developing new products and services.

Proposition 2:

Anxiety affects entrepreneurs' resilience, thereby modulating innovation outcomes, with this relationship mediated by their capacity to generate high-cost signals to stakeholders.

Stewart and Winston (2025) highlight the economic vulnerability and adversity faced by new ventures, emphasizing the need for adaptability to overcome challenges and failures (Stephan, 2022). Ahmed et al. (2022) further argued that existing research inadequately captures the complex interplay between stressors and resilience-development processes. However, Yu and Chen (2025) emphasized the protective role of resilience, as in the case of Covid-19, where higher levels of resilience were connected to lower psychological distress (Killgore et al., 2020; Ran et al., 2020).

Thus, this study proposes that entrepreneurs' psychological resources develop a high level of resilience, enabling them to cope with adversity, challenges, and failures through innovative behavior. The value in this proposition lies in integrating stress responses and anxiety into the relationship of resilience and innovative behavior during times of crisis.

Proposition 3:

Higher levels of entrepreneurial resilience enhance the capacity of entrepreneurs to engage in innovative behavior during periods of crisis.

5. Discussion

Afxentiou and Bezzaz (2025) highlight the significance of stress and uncertainty in business ownership while emphasizing entrepreneurship as a protective factor against mental health challenges (Gish et al., 2022). Additionally, the interplay between adversity and mental health vulnerabilities can inhibit entrepreneurs' capacity to innovate across products, services, and processes (Afxentiou & Bezzaz, 2025; Heinz et al., 2017). Entrepreneurs are expected to cope with both extrinsic and intrinsic demands, overcoming obstacles and addressing adversities inherent in business development and sustainability. Furthermore, Sharma et al. (2025) and Ghosh et al. (2024) argued that personal and organizational resources build resilience, which helps employees cope with work stress and improve performance.

This conceptual study extends existing literature by connecting the individual psychological resources and resilience to the generation of high-cost signals of innovative behavior in distressed environments. From the costly signaling perspective, McAndrew (2021) explains that low-quality signalers attempting to imitate high-quality and high-cost signals deplete internal and external resources, leaving them in a vulnerable position and rendering these strategies counterproductive. In contrast, high-quality signalers possess sufficient resources to invest in high-quality and high-cost signals; consequently, the benefits outweigh the costs (Grafen, 1990). Collectively, these insights highlight the role of psychological resources in fostering strong resilience, which enables entrepreneurs to generate high-cost and high-quality signals of innovative behavior in challenging environments.

The literature review and framework further suggest that lower levels of stress and anxiety facilitate the development of resilience, thereby enhancing entrepreneurs' capacity to project high-cost and high-quality signals to stakeholders. Conversely, excessive psychological strain may deplete critical resources, limiting the ability to engage in costly signaling and, consequently, to sustain innovative outcomes. Furthermore, resilience enables entrepreneurs to withstand adverse environments, sustain stakeholder trust, and develop innovative strategies. In conclusion, the development of a conceptual framework provides a solid foundation for further examining the impact of individual psychological resources on resilience and innovative behavior.

6. Conclusion

This conceptual study examines individual psychological resources (stress responses and anxiety), resilience, signals, and innovative behavior during times of crisis. By integrating entrepreneurial resilience and costly signaling theories, the study develops a conceptual framework that highlights the significance of resilience, the mediating role of costly signals, and the moderating effect of crisis on innovative behavior. The propositions provide a foundation for future empirical research to examine the strength and direction of these relationships. From a practical standpoint, the conceptual framework underscores the importance of fostering psychological resilience among entrepreneurs to sustain innovation.

Future research and limitations

Future research should empirically examine the propositions, particularly the mediating role of costly signals and the moderating effect of crisis conditions. Longitudinal and multi-level studies could provide valuable findings into how stress responses and anxiety evolve and influence resilience and innovative behavior in dynamic environments. Additionally, cross-cultural and industry-specific research would enhance the adaptability of the proposed framework across diverse economic environments. A key limitation of this study lies in its interdisciplinary integration of entrepreneurial resilience and costly signaling theories, which may create conceptual complexity and reduce the clarity of the relationships of resilience, costly signaling, and innovative behavior.

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